

Individual simultaneous first derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper and vanadium in alloy steels and complex materials with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydebenzoylhydrazone

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Manuscript received 7 February 2000, revised 20 February 2001, accepted 19 May 2001

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydebenzoylhydrazone (OHNABH) reacts with V^V and Cu^{II} at pH 5.0 forming respectively yellow and green coloured soluble complexes in 30% DMF. The first derivative amplitude measurements show that Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0–7.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for V at 465 nm and 0–4.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Cu at 443 nm. The sensitivity of the method is greater than the zero order method, and foreign ions like U^{VI} , Th^{IV} , Cr^{VI} which interfere in zero order method, do not interfere even in large excess. Vanadium and copper present in a mixture are simultaneously determined without solving the simultaneous equations by measuring the first derivative amplitudes at 412.6 and 430.2 nm for V and Cu, respectively. The method is applied for the determination of Cu in food materials, V in alloy steels, and both V and Cu in chromium-vanadium steel.

Most of the proposed spectrophotometric methods for the determination of vanadium or copper are less sensitive¹. Those which are more sensitive are either based on catalytic activity of the metal ions^{2,3} or involve extraction into organic solvents⁴ or suffer from the interference of

foreign ions⁵⁻⁸. For the first time, we report here a simple, rapid, sensitive and selective first derivative spectrophotometric method for the determination of vanadium and copper both individually and simultaneously, using 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydebenzoylhydrazone (OHNABH).

Fig. 1. First order derivative spectra of (a) Cu^{II} -OHNABH vs reagent blank and (b) V^V -OHNABH vs reagent blank; $[V^V] = [Cu^{II}] = 1 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[OHNABH] = 5 \times 10^{-5} M$, pH = 5.0.

Results and Discussion

Determination of V^V and Cu^{II} : The first derivative amplitudes of vanadium and copper are plotted against the wavelength (Fig. 1) and the $[V^V$ -OHNABH] and $[Cu^{II}$ -OHNABH] systems show maximum amplitudes at 465 and 443 nm, respectively. The individual analytical studies reveal that Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0–7.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of V^V at 465 nm and 0–4.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Cu^{II} at 443 nm at pH 5.0. The yellow coloured $[V^V$ -OHNABH] and green coloured $[Cu^{II}$ -OHNABH] complexes show maximum and constant

Table 1. Tolerance limit of diverse ions

$V^V = 1.40 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; $Cu^{II} = 0.86 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Ion	Tolerance limit $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$		Ion	Tolerance limit $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	
	V^V	Cu^{II}		V^V	Cu^{II}
EDTA	1600	1400	Pb^{II}	30000	30000
F^-	1250	1100	Mg^{II}	15000	15000
SO_4^{2-}	1000	1050	Mn^{II}	12000	12000
NO_3^-	980	1100	Zn^{II}	10000	10000
Cl^-	950	1000	Al^{III}	6100	6100
I^-	980	900	Zr^{IV}	3500	3500
Br^-	900	950	Li^I	3000	3000
SCN^-	870	860	Hg^{II}	875	825
$S_2O_3^{2-}$	820	810	W^{VI}	680	670
$C_2O_4^{2-}$	630	580	Cd^{II}	460	480
PO_4^{3-}	480	460	Mo^{VI}	250 ^a	280 ^a
Thiourea	320	350	Fe^{III}	850 ^b	930 ^b
Citrate	950	900	Ni^{II}	460 ^a	450 ^a
Tartrate	875	880	Co^{II}	380	420
CO_3^{2-}	550	500	Cr^{VI}	380	420
			U^{VI}	390	350
			Th^{IV}	275	260
			Ce^{IV}	250	250
			Bi^{III}	750	750
			Ag^I	380	350
			Sn^{II}	Ppt.	Ppt.

^aIn presence of 400 μg of PO_4^{3-} . ^bIn presence of 900 μg of F^- .

Table 2. Simultaneous determination of V and Cu

Sample	Amount taken μg ml ⁻¹		Amount found μg ml ⁻¹		% Error	
	V ^V	Cu ^{II}	V ^V	Cu ^{II}	V ^V	Cu ^{II}
1.	0.500	0.320	0.500	0.320	0.00	0.00
2.	0.500	0.640	0.493	0.646	-1.40	+0.94
3.	0.500	0.960	0.503	0.971	+0.60	+1.14
4.	0.500	1.280	0.500	1.303	0.00	+1.79
5.	0.500	1.920	0.506	1.920	+1.20	0.00
6.	0.250	0.320	0.250	0.320	0.00	0.00
7.	0.750	0.320	0.764	0.318	+1.86	-0.62
8.	1.000	0.320	1.014	0.327	+1.40	+2.18
9.	1.500	0.320	1.486	0.322	-0.93	+0.62

absorbance in the pH range 4.5–5.5 with 5-fold excess of reagent. The detection limits of V^V and Cu^{II} in the present method are 0.052 and 0.042 μg ml⁻¹, respectively. The stoichiometry (metal : ligand) and stability constant of [V^V-OHNABH] complex are found to be 1 : 2 and 6.594 × 10¹⁰,

respectively, and the corresponding values for [Cu^{II}-OHNABH] are 2 : 3 and 5.77 × 10²⁰. The experimental data were treated with different statistical methods and the results indicate that the present method is quite accurate. For the V^V system, the angular coefficient (*m*), y-intercept (*b*) correlation coefficient (*r*) and relative standard deviation (%) are 0.1043, -0.00011, 0.9998 and 2.0, respectively; the corresponding values for the Cu^{II} system are 0.157, 0.0014, 0.9998 and 1.0. Many foreign ions do not interfere in the present method. U^{VI}, Th^{IV} and Cr^{VI} which interfere in the zero order method, do not interfere in the first derivative mode as they get resolved from the amplitudes due to vanadium and copper. The interference of Mo^{VI}, Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} can be removed to considerable level by using PO₄³⁻ and F⁻ as masking agents. The tolerance limits of various foreign ions are shown in Table 1.

Simultaneous determination of V^V and Cu^{II} : It can be noticed in Fig. 1 that at 412.6 nm, V^V-OHNABH shows

Table 3. Analysis of standard reference and real samples

Determination of vanadium in steel samples :

Sample	Composition (%)	Content (%)	
		Certified value	Present method*
BCS 483	10.8 W, 3.21 Cr, 0.29 Mn, 1.96 Co ^a , 0.17 Mo ^a , rest Fe ^b	0.540	0.540 ± 0.041
High speed steel	0.75 C, 0.32 Si, 0.30 Mo ^a , 0.30 Mn, 16.96 W, 4.14 Cr, 4.72 Co ^a , 0.012 P, 0.0063 S, rest Fe ^b	0.852	0.852 ± 0.020

Determination of vanadium and copper in chromium-vanadium steel :

Sample	Composition (%)	Amount present (%)		Amount found (%)		Relative error (%)	
		V ^V	Cu ^{II}	V ^V	Cu ^{II}	V ^V	Cu ^{II}
BCS 406/1	0.066 Mn, 1.06 Cr ^c , 0.05 Mo, 0.14 Ni ^c , 0.016 Co	0.190	0.090	0.187	0.092	-1.58	+2.20

Determination of copper in real samples :

	Amount of Cu found*	
	Present method	Na-DDTC method**
Milk sample :	μg ml ⁻¹	
Buffalo	0.164	0.162
Cow	0.284	0.290
Goat	0.196	0.198
Sheep	0.204	0.200
Food sample :		
Wheat flour	0.280	0.284
Rice	0.844	0.840
Tomato	0.556	0.552
Cabbage	0.720	0.710
Apple	0.586	0.593
Banana	0.337	0.340
Liver sample :	μg g ⁻¹ dried liver	
1	1.840	1.860
2	5.260	5.200
3	4.920	4.950
4	3.420	3.360
5	2.840	2.800

*Average of five determinations. **Ref. 12. ^aMasked with PO₄³⁻ (400 μg). ^bMasked with F⁻ (800 μg). ^cMasked with 0.5 ml of 0.1 M citrate.

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considerably high derivative amplitude while Cu^{II}-OHNABH shows zero amplitude (zero cross). The Cu^{II}-OHNABH solution possesses large derivative amplitude at 430.2 nm where the V^V-OHNABH solution shows zero amplitude. At both the wavelengths (412.6 and 430.2 nm) Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.12–7.0 µg ml⁻¹ for V^V and 0.16–4.5 µg ml⁻¹ for Cu^{II}. Hence V^V and Cu^{II} were mixed in various proportions and the amounts were evaluated by measuring the first derivative amplitudes at 412.6 and 430.2 nm and computed from pre-determined calibration plots. The results are presented in Table 2.

Applications : Alloy steel sample solutions were prepared by the reported method⁹. The vanadium content was determined (Table 3). Amounts of copper and vanadium were also determined simultaneously. Solutions of samples of milk¹⁰ food materials¹¹ and sheep liver were prepared by reported methods. Copper present in these samples was determined and compared with those obtained by diethyl dithiocarbamate method¹².

Conclusions : The present method is rapid, sensitive and selective for the determination of vanadium and copper. The derivative method provides their selective determination in some steel samples using zero cross method without using simultaneous equations. The method does not need any critical conditions like heating, extraction or use of surfactants. The present method is more selective than the methods proposed by Zhou *et al.*⁶, Karpinska² for V^V and Tzivanidou and Vasilikiotis⁷, Anipindi *et al.*⁸ for Cu^{II}.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 160-A spectrophotometer and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydebenzoylhydrazone was synthesized by condensing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and benzoylhydrazide in ethanol medium containing small amount of sodium hydroxide¹³ (m.p. 218–220°). The light yellow coloured crystalline product was washed with hot water and its purity was checked by TLC. The structure of the reagent was established by IR and NMR spectra. A 1 × 10⁻³ M solution of the reagent in DMF was used in the studies.

Vanadium(v) and copper(II) stock solutions (1 × 10⁻² M) were prepared by dissolving requisite amounts of cupric sulfate pentahydrate (A.R., B.D.H.) and sodium metavanadate (A.R., Riedel) in distilled water and standardized¹⁴; lower concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution. Buffer solutions were prepared by mixing appropriate volumes of 2 × 10⁻¹ M sodium acetate and 0.2 M acetic acid (pH 3.5–7.0) and their pH was checked. Foreign ions were prepared in suitable concentrations by dissolving appropriate amounts of AnalaR grade samples in distilled water.

Procedure :

Individual determination of V and Cu : To a mixture of buffer solution (pH 5.0; 5 ml), DMF (3 ml) and OHNABH solution (5 × 10⁻³ M; 0.5 ml), variable amounts of vanadium (0.12–7.5 µg ml⁻¹) or copper (0.15–4.50 µg ml⁻¹) were added and made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The first order derivative curves were recorded in the range 405–500 nm and the derivative amplitudes were measured at 465 and 443 nm against the reagent blank for V and Cu, respectively. The data were fed into equation, $y = mx + C$ and found $y = 0.104x - 0.00011$ for V and $y = 0.157x + 0.0014$ for Cu, where x is the amount of metal ion and y the measured derivative amplitude. The calibration plots were drawn for the corrected data.

Simultaneous determination of V and Cu : To solution (1 ml) containing not more than 1.5 µg ml⁻¹ of V and 1.92 µg ml⁻¹ of Cu, the buffer solution (pH 5.0; 4 ml), DMF (3 ml) and OHNABH (5 × 10⁻³ M; 0.5 ml) were added, then diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and the derivative amplitudes were measured at 412.6 and 430.2 nm. The derivative amplitudes were plotted against the amount of V and/or Cu.

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